

Electron
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GULBENKIAN
CIÊNCIA

mfs2023

INL | Braga, Portugal

Influenza A Virus
Liquid Condensates
An Ultrastructural Study

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Influenza A – Structure

Lifecycle steps:

1. Entry
2. Uncoating
3. Replication
4. Trafficking
5. Assembly, Budding and Release

vRNPs Trafficking and Assembly

Maria João Amorim

Sílvia Vale-Costa

Cell Biology of Viral Infection

Introduction

vRNPs Trafficking and Assembly

Bar = 10 μ m

Image adapted from our publications Vale-Costa et al. 2016

Material and Methods

CLEM

Tokuyasu

Multi-Methodology Approach

High Pressure Freezing
Freeze Substitution (HPF-FS)

Tomography
3D Modeling

IAV Liquid Condensates

Correlative Light and Electron Microscopy

A Infected Rab11-expressing stable cell

Bar = 10 μ m

Image adapted from our publications Vale-Costa et al. 2016

IAV Liquid Condensates

Correlative Light and Electron Microscopy

Image adapted from our publications Alenquer et al. 2019

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IAV Liquid Condensates

Tokuyasu

Tokuyasu optimization:

1. Type of Fixation

a) 4% formaldehyde

b) 2% formaldehyde + 0.2% glutaraldehyde

c) 2% formaldehyde + 0.1% glutaraldehyde

d) 2% formaldehyde + 0.05% glutaraldehyde

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tokuyasu

Tested Fixatives

- a) 4% formaldehyde (FA)
- b) 2% FA + 0.2% Glutaraldehyde
- c) 2% FA + 0.1% Glutaraldehyde
- d) 2% FA + 0.05% Glutaraldehyde

Tested Markers

- 1. Golgi (GM130)
- 2. ER (Calnexin)
- 3. Viral Nucleoprotein (NP)
- 4. Rab11 (GFP-Rab11)

Bar = 10 μ m

Images acquired on a Leica SP5 Live Confocal. Analysis done by Fiji.

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tokuyasu

Golgi (GM130) – IgG-Gold 12 nm

ER (Calnexin) – IgG-Gold 12 nm

Bar = 500 nm

Images acquired on a Hitachi H-7650 operating at 100 keV. Analysis done by Fiji.

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tokuyasu

Viral Nucleoprotein (NP) – IgG-Gold 12 nm

Rab11 (GFP-Rab11) – IgG-Gold 18 nm

Bar = 500 nm

Images acquired on a Hitachi H-7650 operating at 100 keV. Analysis done by Fiji.

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HPF-FS

HPF-FS optimization:

1. Type of Specimen Carrier

1. Hats
2. Flat Disks

2. Type of Filler

1. 20% (w/v) Dextran
2. 20% (w/v) Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA)
3. Hexadecene

IAV Liquid Condensates

HPF-FS

Quantification of Single Membrane Vesicles (SMV)
mock, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 hours PI

Quantification of Double Membrane Vesicles (DMV)
mock, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 hours PI

Photomontages acquired on a FEI Tecnai G² Spirit Bio TWIN operating at 120 keV
Analysis done by Fiji multipoint and measure tool (n = 10)

Material and Methods

CLEM

Tokuyasu

Multi-Methodology Approach

High Pressure Freezing
Freeze Substitution (HPF-FS)

Tomography
3D Modeling

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

Establish the 3D Model of IAV inclusions and determine:

- Membrane compartments sustain formation of membraneless organelles?
- Structural features (Double and single membrane vesicles)
- Structures where vRNPs assemble

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

- ▭ Clusters of vesicles
- Single membrane vesicles
- Double membrane vesicles
- Influenza A virus

Tomograms acquired on a FEI Tecnai G² Spirit Bio TWIN operating at 120 keV

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

- ER
- Virions
- Single membrane vesicles
- Double membrane vesicles
- Mitochondria
- Plasma Membrane

Tomograms acquired on a FEI Tecnai G² Spirit Bio TWIN operating at 120 keV
Reconstruction done using Amira

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Tomography and 3D modeling

- Endoplasmic reticulum
- Single membrane vesicles

- vRNPs
- Double membrane vesicles

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

■ Endoplasmic reticulum
■ Single membrane vesicles

■ vRNPs ■ Mitochondria
■ Double membrane vesicles

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

■ Endoplasmic reticulum

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

■ Endoplasmic reticulum
■ Single membrane vesicles

■ vRNPs
■ Budding viruses

■ Plasma membrane

IAV Liquid Condensates

Tomography and 3D modeling

DENV

Welsch S et al (2009)
Cell Host Microbe

MERS

Snijder E et al (2020)
Plos Biology

IAV Liquid Condensates

Conclusions

Are the distinct ER features shown:

- Involved in ER assembly or allow evasion of immune detection?
- Precursors / basic membrane-remodeling stages or by-products of viral protein overexpression?

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Thank-you!

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